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Population Without Adequate Domestic Heating in Europe

Between 2005 and 2021 it decreased by 52.29%

The Eurostat calculates the percentage of the population that is unable to keep the house properly warm. The data for this indicator are collected in the field of the statistics of the European Union on income and on living conditions to monitor the development of poverty and social inclusion in Europe. The collection of data is based on polls.

Ranking of the countries by the value of the population without adequate domestic heating in Europe in 2021. Bulgaria in 2021 was in the top of the ranking for percentage of the population without adequate domestic heating with a value of 23.7%, followed by Lithuania with a value of 22.5%, and from Cyprus with an amount of 19.4%. In the middle of the standings there are Latvia with a value of 4.9%, followed by Belgium with 3.5% and Germany with a value of 3.3%. Austria, Slovenia, and Sweden with a value of 1.7%, close the ranking, followed by Finland with a value of 1.3%. In 2021 on average 7.3% of the European population had economic difficulties that prevented them from keeping the house sufficient hot.

Ranking of European countries for the value of the percentage variation of the value of the population without adequate domestic heating in Europe between 2005 and 2021. Luxembourg is in the first place with a growth of the percentage of the population without resources to adequately heat the home equal to a value of 177.78%, followed by Spain with a value of 51.06% and Sweden with an amount of 21.43%. In the middle of the standings there are Lithuania with -35.34%, followed by Malta with -38.1%, and Cyprus with -42.43%. The Czech Republic close the ranking with -76.34%, followed by Latvia with -83.56%, and Poland with a value of 90.48%. Between 2005 and 2021 the value of the percentage of the population without adequate domestic heating in Europe decreased from a value of 15.36% up to a value of 7.32% or equal to a value of -8.03 equal units at -52.29%.

Clusterization with k-Means algorithm. Below is a clusterization with K-means algorithm optimized with the silhouette coefficient. The data show the presence of the following Clusters or:

- Cluster 1: Cyprus, Portugal, Lithuania, Greece;
- Cluster 2: Germany, Austria, Slovenia, Czech Republic, Estonia, France, the Netherlands, Sweden, Finland, Denmark, Ireland, Slovakia, Luxembourg, Belgium, Spain, Hungary, Malta, Italy, Poland, Latvia.

From the point of view of the median it appears that the C1 value is equal to an amount of 19.4 while the C2 value is equal to an amount of 3.2 units. The following $C1 > C2$ system derives.

Network analysis with the Euclidean distance. A cluster analysis is presented below with the use of the Euclidean distance. A single complex network structure is identified or:

- Luxembourg has a connection with Sweden for an amount of 0.24 units;

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- Sweden has a connection with the Netherlands for an amount of 0.24 units, with Estonia for an amount of 0.26 units and with Iceland for a value of 0.15 units;
- Estonia has a connection with Sweden for an amount of 0.26 units, with the Netherlands for a value of 0.22 units, with Austria for an amount of 0.26 units;
- Austria has a connection with Estonia for an amount of 0.26 units, and with the Netherlands for an amount of 0.26 units;
- The Netherlands have a connection with Sweden by equal to an amount of 0.24 units, with Estonia for a value of 0.22 units, with Austria for a value of 0.26 units, and with the 'Iceland for an amount of 0.25 units;
- Iceland has a connection with Sweden for a value of 0.15 units and with the Netherlands equal to a value of 0.25 units.

The presence of relationships within network analysis does not imply cause-effect relationships. It is the opposite of an analysis oriented to offer an idea of how the effects from one country to another could spread. For example, if the percentage of the population without the ability to guarantee adequate heating to the house were to increase in Austria, then it would also increase in Estonia and the Netherlands. These values are therefore to represent the presence of connections between the historical series trends of the countries analyzed.

Conclusions. The percentage of the population that in European countries has difficulty heating its home adequately has decreased by 52% between 2005 and 2021. It is a very positive trend that highlights an overall improvement in the socio-economic condition of families. However, the historical series analyzed does not take into consideration the period 2021-2022 or 2022-2023, or two exercises in which the increase in the price of gas due to the Russian-Ukraine war may have generated a growth of the percentage of the population with difficulty in heating their home adequately. In fact, the growth of the price of the gas could also cancel the growth of pro-capita income. Finally, the significantly inflationary trend of European economies in the post Covid could further worsen the situation especially of poor families between 2022 and 2023. In any case, in 2021 7.3% of the European population had difficulties in heating their own Housing highlighting a widespread condition of poverty and indigence that could be even more worrying in the event of a manifestation of an economic recession.

Declarations

Data Availability Statement. The data presented in this study are available on request from the corresponding author.

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Declaration of Competing Interest. The author declares that there is no conflict of interests regarding the publication of this manuscript. In addition, the ethical issues, including plagiarism, informed consent, misconduct, data fabrication and/or falsification, double publication.

Software. The authors have used the following software: Gretl for the econometric models, Orange for clusterization and network analysis, and KNIME for machine learning and predictions. They are all free version without licenses.

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Appendix

